

DRYING OF GROUND NEEM SEEDS IN A FLUIDIZED BED DRYER

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ABSTRACT

The drying of ground neem seeds wetted separately with hexane and ethanol was studied. Batch experiments were performed in a fluidized bed dryer as a first step for the recovery of solvents. The wetted material is obtained as an intermediate by-product after two successive leaching steps during the manufacture of a botanical insecticide from the neem seeds. Laboratory scale experiments were carried out in a bed with a conical and a cylindrical bottom, with two material size distributions, and with three gas temperatures. A simple model was developed to describe the drying process. Characteristic drying curves determined with the experimental results were used. Better fluidizing conditions were obtained in the conical bottom bed dryer with particles lying in the range of 0.71-1.2 mm and using a material with a solvent content less than 0.55 kg hexane per kg of dry deoiled seeds and 0.9 kg ethanol per kg of dry exhausted seeds. Agglomeration of particles occurred, particularly, at particle sizes less than 0.71 mm. To obtain a good agreement between calculations and experiments, constants specific for the equipment were used in the literature expressions to calculate transfer coefficients. A fluidized bed dryer seems to be a good alternative, as part of a recovery system for the solvents, required in the processing of neem seeds.

Key Words: fluidized bed, biological materials, solvent recovery

INTRODUCTION

Seed kernels from the neem tree (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) contain about 40 to 45% by weight of non-edible oil and 10 to 12% of a biodegradable mixture that is active against a wide variety of pests (Schmutterer, 1995). Both, the oil and the insecticide mixture are the basis of a commercial neem insecticide manufactured in Nicaragua. The production process (Larson, 1989) comprises the isolation of both substances by two consecutive leaching of ground neem seed kernels in contact with organic solvents. During the first leaching, the oil is removed from seeds with hexane; afterward in a second step, the deoiled seeds (oil-hexane-free seeds) are leached with ethanol to extract the insecticide mixture. At the end of each extraction, about 1.5 kg of hexane and 1.7 kg of ethanol are retained by kilogram of corresponding dry solid (Ramírez 1996). These solvents can be removed from the solid in a convective dryer, such as a fluidized bed, and subsequently recovered in a condenser.

In this work, two types of batch fluidized bed dryers were used to study the drying of both solvents: a cylindrical bed and a bed with a conical part close to the distribution plate. Laboratory scale experiments were carried out with two material size distribution and three gas temperatures. Besides, a simple mathematical model was developed to describe the drying process.

THEORY

In a bed fluidized by a gas, the solid particles are supported by drag forces caused by the gas phase passing through the interstices between particles at some critical velocity. Because of the large surface area available and good mixing between solid and gas, high mass and heat transfer are achieved in fluidized bed dryers. Other advantages are the uniform heat transfer, good control of the drying conditions and low floor area requirements (Coulson et al., 1991).

The mathematical model used to simulate the fluidized bed dryer includes an equipment model that describes the movement of the solid through the equipment, and the residence time of the particles in the dryer and a material model, to describe drying kinetics. In a batch dryer, the residence time is the same for all particles. Furthermore, in a fluidized bed, solid mixing is very effective and the bed of solid particles may be regarded as homogeneous. Solid temperature gradients as well as liquid content gradients exist only at a narrow zone near the distribution plate.

Figure 1. Schematic Pictures of Mass and Heat Transfer between the Gas and Solid in the Dryer.

T: temperature, G: dry air flow, Y: gas humidity (dry basis), X: liquid content (dry basis),

H: enthalpy, N_v : evaporation flux, q_c : heat flux, m_s : mass of solid.

Mass and Energy Balances

Mass and energy balances refer to Figure 1, which describe the interchange of solvent and energy between the solid and the gas phase. Beside the assumptions mentioned above, the solid particles are regarded as spherical and rigid; heat losses are neglected, and the gradients of temperature and liquid content within the particles are not considered.

The mass balances for the solid and the gas phases are:

$$m_s \frac{dX}{dt} = - N_v \cdot A \tag{1}$$

$$G(Y_{\text{out}} - Y_{\text{in}}) = N_v \cdot A \quad (2)$$

Where A is the interfacial area. The energy balances for the solid and the gas phases are:

$$m_s C_{p_s} \frac{dT_s}{dt} = A \{q_c - N_v (H_g - H_{\text{liq}})\} \quad (3)$$

$$G(C_{p_g, \text{out}} T_{g, \text{out}} - C_{p_g, \text{in}} T_{g, \text{in}}) = -A \cdot q_c \quad (4)$$

Where C_{p_s} and C_{p_g} are the humid specific heat capacity of the wet solid and gas, respectively. Equations (1) and (3) were integrated for the following initial conditions:

$$X = X_0 \quad (5)$$

$$T_s = T_{s0} \quad (6)$$

Mass and Heat Transfer Rates

In the calculation of evaporation flux of the volatile component, the distinctive influence of the material, the operation of the drying equipment and the driven force can be conveniently expressed as follows (Keey, 1978):

$$N_v = h_D C_T M (y_s - y_g) \quad (7)$$

Where C_T is the total concentration, h_D is the mass transfer coefficient, M is the solvent molecular weight, y_s and y_g are the molar fraction of solvent at the saturated interface and the bulk of the gas. The relative drying rate, f , is defined as the ratio between the drying rate during the falling rate period, N_v ; and the drying rate during the constant rate period, N_w , and represents an empirical correction to take into account the internal resistance against mass transfer:

$$f = \frac{N_v}{N_w} \quad (8)$$

f can be obtained from experimental drying rates as a function of X . The heat transferred by convection from the air, q_c , is calculated by:

$$q_c = h(T_g - T_s) \quad (9)$$

Heat and Mass Transfer Coefficients

To calculate heat transfer coefficients the following expression were used:

$$Nu = p \cdot Pr^{1/3} Re^r \quad (10)$$

The mass transfer coefficients were calculated by using Chilton-Colburn analogy:

$$h_D = \frac{h}{\rho C_p} \frac{C_T}{C_{Bm}} \left(\frac{Pr}{Sc} \right)^{2/3} \quad (11)$$

The constants p and r were calculated from experimental data and can be regarded as specific for the equipment.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solid Material

Deoiled seeds wetted with hexane and exhausted seeds wetted with ethanol were dried. Fresh ground neem seed kernels were used as raw material. Average composition of this material was 49.7% oil, 18.0% insecticide and 32.3% non-soluble solid matrix. Deoiled seeds were obtained by leaching fresh seed with commercial grade hexane; and exhausted seeds (free of oil and insecticide) were obtained by leaching deoiled seeds with ethanol (97% by weight). After the respective extraction step the solid was dried and sieved to obtain two different size distributions: one with particle diameter from 0.71 to 1.2 mm (called large), and other with diameter from 0.25 to 0.71 mm (called fine). Sieving was performed again after drying to get the size distribution within of the product. Then weight mean diameter and exposed area per dry mass were calculated by assuming spherical particles. Density of solid material was calculated by a gravimetric method. Before drying experiments, the solid material was wetted with solvent (hexane or ethanol) by shaking them in stainless steel cans.

Equipment

Two types of laboratory scale batch fluidized dryers were used: a cylindrical bed and a conical bed (Figure 2). The drying system is shown in Figure 3. The equipment was first preheated until it reached the experiment temperature. Then, wet solids were introduced at the top (5), while the fan (4) was still running. Finally, the throttle (6) was closed. The dryer (1) was isolated to minimize heat losses to the surroundings.

Experiments

Hydrodynamic tests were made to compare the flow behavior between cylindrical and conical bed. The tests were carried out with dry material (1 kg) as well as material wetted with hexane for two different size distributions. Minimum velocity, bubbling velocity and conveying velocity were empirically determined.

Drying experiments were carried out at three gas temperatures: 40, 60 and 80°C with the large size particles, and only at 60°C with the fine particles. During the experiments temperature of gas was measured at the bottom, the middle and the top of the dryer. Moisture content of the solid was determined by taking out samples continuously, more frequently at the beginning. Characteristic drying curves and mass and heat transfer coefficients were obtained from the experimental data.

Figure 2. Cylindrical Bed (left) and Conical Bed (right) Diagrams.

Figure 3. Batch Fluidized Bed Dryer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physical properties of the solids used in the experiments are showed in Table 1. Experimental input data are presented in Tables 2 and 3. In the conical bed dryer a good mixing of the material was obtained. On one side of the cylindrical bed dryer part of the material was stagnant, even with dry material. Since proper fluidizing conditions were not obtained in the cylindrical bed dryer, no further experiments were performed in this bed. Experimental drying rates as a function of liquid content and solid temperature curves as a function of time are compared with simulations in Figure 4 (hexane - deoiled neem seeds) and Figure 5 (ethanol - exhausted neem seeds). These curves correspond to drying of large particles in the conical fluidized bed dryer. An initial cooling period is observed with both solvents.

Table 1. Physical Properties of Solid Materials.

	Deoiled Seed		Exhausted Seed	
	Fine	Large	Fine	Large
Weight Mean Diameter, 10^{-3} m	0.43	0.98	0.51	0.96
Average Density, kg/m^3	910	820	820	690
Exposed Area per Dry Mass, m^2/kg	15.28	7.51	14.28	9.11

Table 2. Data used for Drying Simulations for Hexane Evaporation shown in Figure 4.

$T_{g,in}$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$	u_g m/s	$T_{s,0}$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$	m_s kg	X_0
40	0.8	274	0.890	0.53
60	0.85	289	0.853	0.47
80	0.9	285	0.799	0.50

Table 3. Data used for Drying Simulations for Ethanol Evaporation shown in Figure 5.

$T_{g,in}$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$	u_g m/s	$T_{s,0}$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$	m_s kg	X_0
40	0.96	283	0.657	0.84
60	0.99	289	0.737	0.75
80	1.05	305	0.579	0.90

Figure 4. Results from Drying Experiments and Simulations for Hexane - Deoiled Neem Seeds System. Drying Rate Curves (left) and Temperature Curves for the Material (right).

Figure 5. Results from Drying Experiments and Simulations for Ethanol - Exhausted Neem Seeds System. Drying Curves (left) and Temperature Curves for the Material (right).

CONCLUSIONS

Wet ground neem seeds cannot be treated directly after leaching to remove the solvent in a fluidized bed dryer. To obtain good fluidization conditions, the solvent content should be previously reduced by a mechanical separation step, e.g. filtration or centrifugation.

Solvent content was reduced from 1.5 to less than 0.55 kg hexane per kg of dry deoiled seeds and from 1.7 to 0.9 kg ethanol per kg of dry exhausted seeds in order to obtain appropriate fluidization conditions in the conical bed dryer. In the cylindrical bed dryer, stagnation of solids occurred even at these levels of solvent content. This was due to the lower velocities achieved in the cylindrical bed dryer.

A certain degree of particle agglomeration, particularly when drying particles of small sizes, was observed.

At an initial stage, a reduction of solid temperature took place in all the experiments. The diminishing of solid temperature was more pronounced during the drying of ground seeds containing hexane, which is in accordance with the faster initial drying rate of the wet material containing this solvent.

The agreement between experimental results and simulations was not good for the drying of ground neem seeds containing hexane. The agreement was better for the ground seeds containing ethanol. The use of the relative drying rate to account for the resistance against mass transfer is limited by the fact that it does not provide an equivalent correction to account for resistances against heat transfer. A model considering temperature and solvent content gradients within the particle would surmount this limitation.

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NOTATION

A	Total surface area of particles	m^2
C_{Bm}	Mean logarithmic molar concentration of the dry air	$kmol/m^3$
C_p	Specific heat capacity	$kJ/kg\ K$
C_T	Total molar concentration	$kmol/m^3$
f	Relative drying rate	-
G	Gas flow	kg/s
H	Enthalpy	kJ/kg
h	Heat transfer coefficient	$kJ/m^2\ s\ K$
h_D	Mass transfer coefficient	m/s
M	Molecular weight	$kg/kmol$
m_s	Dry solid mass	kg
N_v	Drying rate per surface of solid	kg/m^2s
N_w	Drying rate during constant rate period	kg/m^2s
q	Heat flux	kJ/m^2s
ρ	Density	kg/m^3
T	Temperature	K
t	Time	s
u	Gas velocity	m/s
X	Solvent content of the solid	kg/kg
Y	Solvent content of the gas	kg/kg
y	Molar fraction of solvent	$kmol/kmol$

Subscripts

0	initial value or condition	liq	liquid
c	convective	out	outlet
g	gas	s	solid
in	inlet		

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